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General Linear Model

[Jeu_de_données2]

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Dependent Variable		
1	1	1	1	P1C1D1B1A1 Dominique		
			2	P1C1D1B2A2 Elisabeth		
			3	P1C1D1B3A3 Magali		
		2	1	1	P1C1D2B1A4 Michèle	
				2	P1C1D2B2A5 Jocelyne	
				3	P1C1D2B3A6 Agnès	
		3	1	1	P1C1D3B1A7 Christiane	
				2	P1C1D3B2A8 Maryse	
				3	P1C1D3B3A9 AnneMarie	
	2	1	1	1	P1C2D1B1A1 0Jacqueline	
				2	P1C2D1B2A1 1Danielle	
				3	P1C2D1B3A1 2Sylviane	
			2	1	1	P1C2D2B1A1 3Geneviève
					2	P1C2D2B2A1 4Valérie
					3	P1C2D2B3A1 5Sandrine
3			1	1	P1C2D3B1A1 6Christelle	
				2	P1C2D3B2A1 7Carole	
				3	P1C2D3B3A1 8Stéphanie	
2	1	1	1	P2C1D1B1A1 9Colette		
			2	P2C1D1B2A2 0Josette		
			3	P2C1D1B3A2 1Liliane		

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Dependent Variable
		2	1	P2C1D2B1A2 2Eliane
			2	P2C1D2B2A2 3Jeannine
			3	P2C1D2B3A2 4Yvette
		3	1	P2C1D3B1A2 5Gisèle
			2	P2C1D3B2A2 6Denise
			3	P2C1D3B3A2 7Francine
	2	1	1	P2C2D1B1A2 8Thérèse
			2	P2C2D1B2A2 9Ghislaine
			3	P2C2D1B3A3 0Delphine
		2	1	P2C2D2B1A3 1Céline
			2	P2C2D2B2A3 2Cécile
			3	P2C2D2B3A3 3Sabine
		3	1	P2C2D3B1A3 4Sandra
			2	P2C2D3B2A3 5Laure
			3	P2C2D3B3A3 6Claire

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
P1C1D1B1 A 1 Dominique	9,28	1,672	126
P1C1D1B2 A 2 Elisabeth	6,71	2,988	126
P1C1D1B3 A 3 Magali	3,70	2,978	126
P1C1D2B1 A 4 Michèle	9,30	1,498	126
P1C1D2B2 A 5 Jocelyne	6,47	2,979	126
P1C1D2B3 A6 Agnès	3,79	3,097	126
P1C1D3B1 A 7 Christiane	8,83	2,117	126
P1C1D3B2 A 8 Maryse	6,95	2,878	126
P1C1D3B3 A 9 Anne-Marie	6,21	3,358	126
P1C2D1B1 A 10 Jacqueline	9,58	,773	126
P1C2D1B2 A 11 Danielle	7,91	2,294	126
P1C2D1B3 A 12 Sylviane	5,95	2,805	126
P1C2D2B1 A 13 Geneviève	9,48	1,122	126
P1C2D2B2 A 14 Valérie	7,98	2,130	126
P1C2D2B3 A15 Sandrine	5,89	2,737	126
P1C2D3B1 A 16 Christelle	9,02	1,725	126
P1C2D3B2 A 17 Carole	7,71	2,507	126
P1C2D3B3 A 18 Stéphanie	7,31	3,068	126
P2C1D1B1 A 19 Colette	8,71	1,639	126
P2C1D1B2 A 20 Josette	6,43	2,844	126
P2C1D1B3 A21 Liliane	3,63	3,302	126
P2C1D2B1 A 22 Eliane	8,48	1,946	126
P2C1D2B2 A 23 Jeannine	6,52	2,950	126
P2C1D2B3 A 24 Yvette	3,31	3,123	126
P2C1D3B1 A 25 Gisèle	8,33	2,287	126
P2C1D3B2 A 26 Denise	6,55	3,095	126
P2C1D3B3 A27 Francine	6,11	3,585	126
P2C2D1B1 A 28 Thérèse	8,83	1,457	126
P2C2D1B2 A 29 Ghislaine	7,33	2,429	126
P2C2D1B3 A 30 Delphine	5,52	2,995	126
P2C2D2B1 A 31 Céline	8,79	1,665	126

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
P2C2D2B2 A 32 Cécile	7,03	2,635	126
P2C2D2B3 A 33 Sabine	5,18	3,089	126
P2C2D3B1 A 34 Sandra	8,53	1,909	126
P2C2D3B2 A 35 Laure	7,40	2,745	126
P2C2D3B3 A 36 Claire	6,74	3,257	126

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
Physical.activity	Pillai's Trace	,241	39,586 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,759	39,586 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,317	39,586 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,317	39,586 ^b	1,000	125,000
Drinking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,480	115,414 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,520	115,414 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,923	115,414 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,923	115,414 ^b	1,000	125,000
Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,202	15,730 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,798	15,730 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,254	15,730 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,254	15,730 ^b	2,000	124,000
Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,705	148,166 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,295	148,166 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	2,390	148,166 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	2,390	148,166 ^b	2,000	124,000
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,057	7,541 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,943	7,541 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,060	7,541 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,060	7,541 ^b	1,000	125,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,038	2,422 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,962	2,422 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,039	2,422 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,039	2,422 ^b	2,000	124,000
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,164	12,178 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,836	12,178 ^b	2,000	124,000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Pillai's Trace	,000	,241
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,241
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,241
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,241
Drinking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,000	,480
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,480
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,480
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,480
Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,000	,202
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,202
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,202
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,202
Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,705
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,705
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,705
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,705
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,007	,057
	Wilks' Lambda	,007	,057
	Hotelling's Trace	,007	,057
	Roy's Largest Root	,007	,057
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,093	,038
	Wilks' Lambda	,093	,038
	Hotelling's Trace	,093	,038
	Roy's Largest Root	,093	,038
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,000	,164
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,164

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
	Hotelling's Trace	,196	12,178 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,196	12,178 ^b	2,000	124,000
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,012	,723 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,988	,723 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,012	,723 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,012	,723 ^b	2,000	124,000
Physical.activity * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,057	3,769 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,943	3,769 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,061	3,769 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,061	3,769 ^b	2,000	124,000
Drinking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,403	41,897 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,597	41,897 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,676	41,897 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,676	41,897 ^b	2,000	124,000
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,045	2,903 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,955	2,903 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,047	2,903 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,047	2,903 ^b	2,000	124,000
Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,357	16,936 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,643	16,936 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,555	16,936 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,555	16,936 ^b	4,000	122,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,018	,552 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,982	,552 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,018	,552 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,018	,552 ^b	4,000	122,000
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,185	6,916 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,815	6,916 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,227	6,916 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,227	6,916 ^b	4,000	122,000
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,095	3,216 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,905	3,216 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,105	3,216 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,105	3,216 ^b	4,000	122,000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,164
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,164
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,487	,012
	Wilks' Lambda	,487	,012
	Hotelling's Trace	,487	,012
	Roy's Largest Root	,487	,012
Physical.activity * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,026	,057
	Wilks' Lambda	,026	,057
	Hotelling's Trace	,026	,057
	Roy's Largest Root	,026	,057
Drinking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,403
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,403
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,403
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,403
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,059	,045
	Wilks' Lambda	,059	,045
	Hotelling's Trace	,059	,045
	Roy's Largest Root	,059	,045
Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,357
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,357
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,357
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,357
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,698	,018
	Wilks' Lambda	,698	,018
	Hotelling's Trace	,698	,018
	Roy's Largest Root	,698	,018
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,185
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,185
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,185
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,185
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,015	,095
	Wilks' Lambda	,015	,095
	Hotelling's Trace	,015	,095
	Roy's Largest Root	,015	,095

a. Design: Intercept

Within Subjects Design: Physical.activity + Drinking.habits + Diagnosis + Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits + Physical.activity * Diagnosis + Drinking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Behavior + Drinking.habits * Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior + Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior + Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

b. Exact statistic

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Epsilon ^b Greenhouse-Geisser
Physical.activity	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Drinking.habits	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Diagnosis	,377	120,887	2	,000	,616
Behavior	,839	21,798	2	,000	,861
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	,871	17,118	2	,000	,886
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	,852	19,802	2	,000	,871
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	,993	,821	2	,663	,993
Physical.activity * Behavior	,996	,520	2	,771	,996
Drinking.habits * Behavior	,932	8,667	2	,013	,937
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	,986	1,710	2	,425	,986
Diagnosis * Behavior	,101	282,973	9	,000	,487
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	,692	45,524	9	,000	,863
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,807	26,410	9	,002	,903
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,918	10,494	9	,312	,960

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Epsilon ^b	
	Huynh-Feldt	Lower-bound
Physical.activity	1,000	1,000
Drinking.habits	1,000	1,000
Diagnosis	,619	,500
Behavior	,872	,500
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	1,000	1,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	,898	,500
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	,883	,500
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	1,000	,500
Physical.activity * Behavior	1,000	,500
Drinking.habits * Behavior	,951	,500
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	1,000	,500
Diagnosis * Behavior	,494	,250
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	,890	,250
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,933	,250
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,994	,250

Tests the null hypothesis that the error covariance matrix of the orthonormalized transformed dependent variables is proportional to an identity matrix.

-

a. Design: Intercept

Within Subjects Design: Physical.activity + Drinking.habits + Diagnosis + Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits + Physical.activity * Diagnosis + Drinking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Behavior + Drinking.habits * Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior + Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior + Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

b. May be used to adjust the degrees of freedom for the averaged tests of significance. Corrected tests are displayed in the Tests of Within-Subjects Effects table.

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Physical.activity	Sphericity Assumed	261,927	1	261,927
	Greenhouse-Geisser	261,927	1,000	261,927
	Huynh-Feldt	261,927	1,000	261,927
	Lower-bound	261,927	1,000	261,927
Error(Physical.activity)	Sphericity Assumed	827,073	125	6,617
	Greenhouse-Geisser	827,073	125,000	6,617
	Huynh-Feldt	827,073	125,000	6,617
	Lower-bound	827,073	125,000	6,617
Drinking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	998,321	1	998,321
	Greenhouse-Geisser	998,321	1,000	998,321
	Huynh-Feldt	998,321	1,000	998,321
	Lower-bound	998,321	1,000	998,321
Error(Drinking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed	1081,235	125	8,650
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1081,235	125,000	8,650
	Huynh-Feldt	1081,235	125,000	8,650
	Lower-bound	1081,235	125,000	8,650
Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	331,580	2	165,790
	Greenhouse-Geisser	331,580	1,232	269,039
	Huynh-Feldt	331,580	1,239	267,720
	Lower-bound	331,580	1,000	331,580
Error(Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	1931,420	250	7,726
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1931,420	154,058	12,537
	Huynh-Feldt	1931,420	154,817	12,476
	Lower-bound	1931,420	125,000	15,451
Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	10076,700	2	5038,350
	Greenhouse-Geisser	10076,700	1,722	5850,555
	Huynh-Feldt	10076,700	1,744	5777,392
	Lower-bound	10076,700	1,000	10076,700
Error(Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	6202,633	250	24,811
	Greenhouse-Geisser	6202,633	215,294	28,810
	Huynh-Feldt	6202,633	218,020	28,450
	Lower-bound	6202,633	125,000	49,621
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	18,541	1	18,541
	Greenhouse-Geisser	18,541	1,000	18,541
	Huynh-Feldt	18,541	1,000	18,541
	Lower-bound	18,541	1,000	18,541

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Sphericity Assumed	39,586	,000	,241
	Greenhouse-Geisser	39,586	,000	,241
	Huynh-Feldt	39,586	,000	,241
	Lower-bound	39,586	,000	,241
Error(Physical.activity)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Drinking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	115,414	,000	,480
	Greenhouse-Geisser	115,414	,000	,480
	Huynh-Feldt	115,414	,000	,480
	Lower-bound	115,414	,000	,480
Error(Drinking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	21,460	,000	,147
	Greenhouse-Geisser	21,460	,000	,147
	Huynh-Feldt	21,460	,000	,147
	Lower-bound	21,460	,000	,147
Error(Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	203,073	,000	,619
	Greenhouse-Geisser	203,073	,000	,619
	Huynh-Feldt	203,073	,000	,619
	Lower-bound	203,073	,000	,619
Error(Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	7,541	,007	,057
	Greenhouse-Geisser	7,541	,007	,057
	Huynh-Feldt	7,541	,007	,057
	Lower-bound	7,541	,007	,057

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed	307,348	125	2,459
	Greenhouse-Geisser	307,348	125,000	2,459
	Huynh-Feldt	307,348	125,000	2,459
	Lower-bound	307,348	125,000	2,459
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	8,429	2	4,215
	Greenhouse-Geisser	8,429	1,772	4,758
	Huynh-Feldt	8,429	1,795	4,695
	Lower-bound	8,429	1,000	8,429
Error(Physical. activity*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	389,571	250	1,558
	Greenhouse-Geisser	389,571	221,446	1,759
	Huynh-Feldt	389,571	224,398	1,736
	Lower-bound	389,571	125,000	3,117
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	56,958	2	28,479
	Greenhouse-Geisser	56,958	1,743	32,682
	Huynh-Feldt	56,958	1,765	32,265
	Lower-bound	56,958	1,000	56,958
Error(Drinking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	436,153	250	1,745
	Greenhouse-Geisser	436,153	217,847	2,002
	Huynh-Feldt	436,153	220,666	1,977
	Lower-bound	436,153	125,000	3,489
Physical.activity * Drinking. habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	2,844	2	1,422
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,844	1,987	1,432
	Huynh-Feldt	2,844	2,000	1,422
	Lower-bound	2,844	1,000	2,844
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	452,600	250	1,810
	Greenhouse-Geisser	452,600	248,361	1,822
	Huynh-Feldt	452,600	250,000	1,810
	Lower-bound	452,600	125,000	3,621
Physical.activity * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	13,610	2	6,805
	Greenhouse-Geisser	13,610	1,992	6,834
	Huynh-Feldt	13,610	2,000	6,805
	Lower-bound	13,610	1,000	13,610
Error(Physical. activity*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	478,056	250	1,912
	Greenhouse-Geisser	478,056	248,958	1,920
	Huynh-Feldt	478,056	250,000	1,912
	Lower-bound	478,056	125,000	3,824

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	2,705	,069	,021
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,705	,076	,021
	Huynh-Feldt	2,705	,075	,021
	Lower-bound	2,705	,103	,021
Error(Physical. activity*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	16,324	,000	,116
	Greenhouse-Geisser	16,324	,000	,116
	Huynh-Feldt	16,324	,000	,116
	Lower-bound	16,324	,000	,116
Error(Drinking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Drinking. habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	,786	,457	,006
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,786	,456	,006
	Huynh-Feldt	,786	,457	,006
	Lower-bound	,786	,377	,006
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	3,559	,030	,028
	Greenhouse-Geisser	3,559	,030	,028
	Huynh-Feldt	3,559	,030	,028
	Lower-bound	3,559	,062	,028
Error(Physical. activity*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Drinking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	381,600	2	190,800
	Greenhouse-Geisser	381,600	1,874	203,680
	Huynh-Feldt	381,600	1,901	200,736
	Lower-bound	381,600	1,000	381,600
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	903,178	250	3,613
	Greenhouse-Geisser	903,178	234,190	3,857
	Huynh-Feldt	903,178	237,625	3,801
	Lower-bound	903,178	125,000	7,225
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	8,626	2	4,313
	Greenhouse-Geisser	8,626	1,973	4,372
	Huynh-Feldt	8,626	2,000	4,313
	Lower-bound	8,626	1,000	8,626
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	409,152	250	1,637
	Greenhouse-Geisser	409,152	246,622	1,659
	Huynh-Feldt	409,152	250,000	1,637
	Lower-bound	409,152	125,000	3,273
Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	1037,900	4	259,475
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1037,900	1,948	532,913
	Huynh-Feldt	1037,900	1,978	524,723
	Lower-bound	1037,900	1,000	1037,900
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	2895,600	500	5,791
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2895,600	243,450	11,894
	Huynh-Feldt	2895,600	247,250	11,711
	Lower-bound	2895,600	125,000	23,165
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	4,728	4	1,182
	Greenhouse-Geisser	4,728	3,450	1,371
	Huynh-Feldt	4,728	3,560	1,328
	Lower-bound	4,728	1,000	4,728
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	951,105	500	1,902
	Greenhouse-Geisser	951,105	431,252	2,205
	Huynh-Feldt	951,105	444,984	2,137
	Lower-bound	951,105	125,000	7,609
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	62,689	4	15,672
	Greenhouse-Geisser	62,689	3,612	17,357
	Huynh-Feldt	62,689	3,732	16,796
	Lower-bound	62,689	1,000	62,689

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Drinking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	52,813	,000	,297
	Greenhouse-Geisser	52,813	,000	,297
	Huynh-Feldt	52,813	,000	,297
	Lower-bound	52,813	,000	,297
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	2,635	,074	,021
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,635	,074	,021
	Huynh-Feldt	2,635	,074	,021
	Lower-bound	2,635	,107	,021
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	44,805	,000	,264
	Greenhouse-Geisser	44,805	,000	,264
	Huynh-Feldt	44,805	,000	,264
	Lower-bound	44,805	,000	,264
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	,621	,647	,005
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,621	,624	,005
	Huynh-Feldt	,621	,629	,005
	Lower-bound	,621	,432	,005
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	7,525	,000	,057
	Greenhouse-Geisser	7,525	,000	,057
	Huynh-Feldt	7,525	,000	,057
	Lower-bound	7,525	,007	,057

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Error(Drinking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	1041,367	500	2,083
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1041,367	451,454	2,307
	Huynh-Feldt	1041,367	466,545	2,232
	Lower-bound	1041,367	125,000	8,331
Physical.activity * Drinking. habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	18,501	4	4,625
	Greenhouse-Geisser	18,501	3,839	4,820
	Huynh-Feldt	18,501	3,976	4,654
	Lower-bound	18,501	1,000	18,501
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	737,888	500	1,476
	Greenhouse-Geisser	737,888	479,844	1,538
	Huynh-Feldt	737,888	496,944	1,485
	Lower-bound	737,888	125,000	5,903

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Error(Drinking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Drinking. habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	3,134	,015	,024
	Greenhouse-Geisser	3,134	,016	,024
	Huynh-Feldt	3,134	,015	,024
	Lower-bound	3,134	,079	,024
Error(Physical. activity*Drinking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior
Physical.activity	Linear			
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear			
Drinking.habits		Linear		
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear		
Diagnosis			Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear	
			Quadratic	
Behavior				Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Behavior)				Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear		
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear		
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear	
			Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear
				Quadratic
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear
				Quadratic

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Type III Sum of Squares
Physical.activity	Linear				261,927
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				827,073
Drinking.habits		Linear			998,321
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			1081,235
Diagnosis			Linear		194,540
			Quadratic		137,040
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		1391,085
			Quadratic		540,335
Behavior				Linear	10076,190
				Quadratic	,510
Error(Behavior)				Linear	4283,893
				Quadratic	1918,740
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			18,541
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			307,348
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,453
			Quadratic		7,976
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		183,006
			Quadratic		206,565
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		45,027
			Quadratic		11,931
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		239,265
			Quadratic		196,888
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,230
			Quadratic		1,614
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		229,228
			Quadratic		223,372
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	11,196
				Quadratic	2,414
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	231,888
				Quadratic	246,169
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	381,440
				Quadratic	,159
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	567,310
				Quadratic	335,869

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	df
Physical.activity	Linear				1
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				125
Drinking.habits		Linear			1
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			125
Diagnosis			Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		125
			Quadratic		125
Behavior				Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Behavior)				Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			1
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			125
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		125
			Quadratic		125
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		125
			Quadratic		125
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		125
			Quadratic		125
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	125
				Quadratic	125

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean Square
Physical.activity	Linear				261,927
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				6,617
Drinking.habits		Linear			998,321
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			8,650
Diagnosis			Linear		194,540
			Quadratic		137,040
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		11,129
			Quadratic		4,323
Behavior				Linear	10076,190
				Quadratic	,510
Error(Behavior)				Linear	34,271
				Quadratic	15,350
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			18,541
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			2,459
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,453
			Quadratic		7,976
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		1,464
			Quadratic		1,653
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		45,027
			Quadratic		11,931
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		1,914
			Quadratic		1,575
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,230
			Quadratic		1,614
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,834
			Quadratic		1,787
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	11,196
				Quadratic	2,414
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	1,855
				Quadratic	1,969
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	381,440
				Quadratic	,159
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	4,538
				Quadratic	2,687

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	F
Physical.activity	Linear				39,586
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Drinking.habits		Linear			115,414
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		17,481
			Quadratic		31,702
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	294,014
				Quadratic	,033
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			7,541
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,309
			Quadratic		4,827
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		23,524
			Quadratic		7,575
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,671
			Quadratic		,903
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	6,035
				Quadratic	1,226
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	84,046
				Quadratic	,059
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Sig.
Physical.activity	Linear				,000
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Drinking.habits		Linear			,000
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		,000
			Quadratic		,000
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,856
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			,007
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,579
			Quadratic		,030
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		,000
			Quadratic		,007
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,414
			Quadratic		,344
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	,015
				Quadratic	,270
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,808
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Linear				,241
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Drinking.habits		Linear			,480
Error(Drinking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		,123
			Quadratic		,202
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	,702
				Quadratic	,000
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits	Linear	Linear			,057
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,002
			Quadratic		,037
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		,158
			Quadratic		,057
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,005
			Quadratic		,007
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	,046
				Quadratic	,010
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	,402
				Quadratic	,000
Error(Drinking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Type III Sum of Squares
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	5,589
				Quadratic	3,037
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	185,495
				Quadratic	223,657
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	676,698
				Quadratic	76,455
			Quadratic	Linear	255,054
				Quadratic	29,693
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	1398,052
				Quadratic	600,545
			Quadratic	Linear	528,863
				Quadratic	368,140
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	2,032
				Quadratic	,066
			Quadratic	Linear	,556
				Quadratic	2,074
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	275,968
				Quadratic	249,851
			Quadratic	Linear	203,610
				Quadratic	221,676
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	45,240
				Quadratic	5,720
			Quadratic	Linear	9,524
				Quadratic	2,205
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	245,510
				Quadratic	189,613
			Quadratic	Linear	322,226
				Quadratic	284,018
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,716
				Quadratic	1,223
			Quadratic	Linear	,011
				Quadratic	16,551
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	167,284
				Quadratic	197,694
			Quadratic	Linear	193,656
				Quadratic	179,254

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	df
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
			Quadratic	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
			Quadratic	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
			Quadratic	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
			Quadratic	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean Square
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	5,589
				Quadratic	3,037
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	1,484
				Quadratic	1,789
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	676,698
				Quadratic	76,455
			Quadratic	Linear	255,054
				Quadratic	29,693
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	11,184
				Quadratic	4,804
			Quadratic	Linear	4,231
				Quadratic	2,945
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	2,032
				Quadratic	,066
			Quadratic	Linear	,556
				Quadratic	2,074
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	2,208
				Quadratic	1,999
			Quadratic	Linear	1,629
				Quadratic	1,773
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	45,240
				Quadratic	5,720
			Quadratic	Linear	9,524
				Quadratic	2,205
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	1,964
				Quadratic	1,517
			Quadratic	Linear	2,578
				Quadratic	2,272
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,716
				Quadratic	1,223
			Quadratic	Linear	,011
				Quadratic	16,551
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1,338
				Quadratic	1,582
			Quadratic	Linear	1,549
				Quadratic	1,434

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	F
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	3,766
				Quadratic	1,698
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	60,504
				Quadratic	15,914
			Quadratic	Linear	60,283
				Quadratic	10,082
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,920
				Quadratic	,033
			Quadratic	Linear	,341
				Quadratic	1,170
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	23,034
				Quadratic	3,771
			Quadratic	Linear	3,695
				Quadratic	,970
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,535
				Quadratic	,773
			Quadratic	Linear	,007
				Quadratic	11,542
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Sig.
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,055
				Quadratic	,195
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,000
			Quadratic	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,002
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,339
				Quadratic	,856
			Quadratic	Linear	,560
				Quadratic	,282
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,054
			Quadratic	Linear	,057
				Quadratic	,327
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,466
				Quadratic	,381
			Quadratic	Linear	,934
				Quadratic	,001
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,029
				Quadratic	,013
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	,326
				Quadratic	,113
			Quadratic	Linear	,325
				Quadratic	,075
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,007
				Quadratic	,000
			Quadratic	Linear	,003
				Quadratic	,009
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	,156
				Quadratic	,029
			Quadratic	Linear	,029
				Quadratic	,008
Error(Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,004
				Quadratic	,006
			Quadratic	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,085
Error(Physical.activity*Drinking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	228466,681	1	228466,681	2587,278	,000	,954
Error	11037,986	125	88,304			

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Grand Mean

Measure: MEASURE_1

Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
7,097	,140	6,821	7,373

2. Physical.activity

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	7,337	,130	7,079	7,595
2	6,857	,158	6,545	7,169

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Physical.activity	(J) Physical.activity	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
					Lower Bound
1	2	,481 [*]	,076	,000	,329
2	1	-,481 [*]	,076	,000	-,632

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Physical.activity	(J) Physical.activity	95% Confidence Interval for ...
		Upper Bound
1	2	,632
2	1	-,329

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,241	39,586 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,241
Wilks' lambda	,759	39,586 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,241
Hotelling's trace	,317	39,586 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,241
Roy's largest root	,317	39,586 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,241

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Physical.activity. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

3. Drinking.habits

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Drinking.habits	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,628	,160	6,311	6,944
2	7,566	,131	7,307	7,825

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Drinking.habits	(J) Drinking.habits	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence
					Lower Bound
1	2	-,938 [*]	,087	,000	-1,111
2	1	,938 [*]	,087	,000	,765

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Drinking.habits	(J) Drinking.habits	95% Confidence
		Interval for ^b ...
1	2	Upper Bound -,765
2	1	Upper Bound 1,111

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,480	115,414 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,480
Wilks' lambda	,520	115,414 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,480
Hotelling's trace	,923	115,414 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,480
Roy's largest root	,923	115,414 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,480

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Drinking.habits. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

4. Diagnosis

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,966	,145	6,679	7,254
2	6,851	,146	6,562	7,140
3	7,474	,162	7,153	7,794

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Diagnosis	(J) Diagnosis	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
					Lower Bound
1	2	,115 [*]	,047	,015	,023
	3	-,507 [*]	,121	,000	-,747
2	1	-,115 [*]	,047	,015	-,207
	3	-,622 [*]	,117	,000	-,855
3	1	,507 [*]	,121	,000	,267
	2	,622 [*]	,117	,000	,390

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Diagnosis	(J) Diagnosis	95% Confidence Interval for ^b ..
		Upper Bound
1	2	,207
	3	-,267
2	1	-,023
	3	-,390
3	1	,747
	2	,855

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,202	15,730 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,202
Wilks' lambda	,798	15,730 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,202
Hotelling's trace	,254	15,730 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,202
Roy's largest root	,254	15,730 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,202

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Diagnosis. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

5. Behavior

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	8,930	,094	8,743	9,117
2	7,082	,187	6,712	7,452
3	5,279	,218	4,849	5,710

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Behavior	(J) Behavior	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	1,848 [*]	,174	,000	1,504	2,191
	3	3,651 [*]	,213	,000	3,229	4,072
2	1	-1,848 [*]	,174	,000	-2,191	-1,504
	3	1,803 [*]	,152	,000	1,503	2,103
3	1	-3,651 [*]	,213	,000	-4,072	-3,229
	2	-1,803 [*]	,152	,000	-2,103	-1,503

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,705	148,166 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,705
Wilks' lambda	,295	148,166 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,705
Hotelling's trace	2,390	148,166 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,705
Roy's largest root	2,390	148,166 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,705

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Behavior. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

6. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,804	,158	6,492	7,116
	2	7,870	,121	7,631	8,110
2	1	6,451	,173	6,110	6,793
	2	7,262	,156	6,954	7,570

7. Physical.activity * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	7,189	,138	6,916	7,462
	2	7,151	,136	6,882	7,420
	3	7,672	,153	7,369	7,975
2	1	6,743	,166	6,414	7,073
	2	6,552	,170	6,215	6,888
	3	7,275	,180	6,918	7,632

8. Physical.activity * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	9,247	,089	9,072	9,423
	2	7,290	,187	6,920	7,659
	3	5,475	,210	5,060	5,890
2	1	8,612	,127	8,361	8,864
	2	6,874	,198	6,482	7,267
	3	5,083	,233	4,623	5,544

9. Drinking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,411	,169	6,076	6,747
	2	6,310	,171	5,971	6,648
	3	7,163	,180	6,807	7,519
2	1	7,521	,138	7,247	7,795
	2	7,393	,138	7,121	7,665
	3	7,784	,158	7,471	8,097

10. Drinking.habits * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Drinking.habits	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	8,820	,116	8,591	9,049
	2	6,604	,220	6,170	7,039
	3	4,459	,242	3,981	4,937
2	1	9,040	,088	8,866	9,214
	2	7,560	,171	7,222	7,897
	3	6,099	,216	5,672	6,526

11. Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	9,101	,091	8,922	9,280
	2	7,095	,206	6,688	7,502
	3	4,702	,233	4,242	5,163
2	1	9,014	,101	8,815	9,213
	2	6,998	,204	6,594	7,402
	3	4,542	,235	4,077	5,007
3	1	8,675	,140	8,398	8,951
	2	7,153	,218	6,720	7,585
	3	6,593	,267	6,065	7,122

12. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% ...
					Lower Bound
1	1	1	6,563	,172	6,222
		2	6,519	,168	6,186
		3	7,331	,177	6,980
	2	1	7,815	,131	7,555
		2	7,783	,129	7,527
		3	8,013	,156	7,704
2	1	1	6,259	,186	5,891
		2	6,101	,191	5,723
		3	6,995	,200	6,599
	2	1	7,228	,166	6,899
		2	7,003	,173	6,661
		3	7,556	,179	7,201

12. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	95% Confidence .
			Upper Bound
1	1	1	6,905
		2	6,851
		3	7,681
	2	1	8,075
		2	8,039
		3	8,322
2	1	1	6,628
		2	6,478
		3	7,391
	2	1	7,556
		2	7,344
		3	7,911

13. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	9,135	,120	8,897	9,372
		2	6,712	,233	6,251	7,172
		3	4,566	,241	4,089	5,043
	2	1	9,360	,079	9,203	9,517
		2	7,868	,167	7,537	8,198
		3	6,384	,210	5,969	6,799
2	1	1	8,505	,141	8,226	8,784
		2	6,497	,226	6,050	6,944
		3	4,352	,251	3,854	4,850
	2	1	8,720	,128	8,465	8,974
		2	7,251	,193	6,870	7,632
		3	5,815	,239	5,342	6,288

14. Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	9,429	,098	9,235	9,622
		2	7,313	,214	6,890	7,737
		3	4,825	,228	4,374	5,277
	2	1	9,393	,093	9,209	9,577
		2	7,222	,206	6,815	7,630
		3	4,837	,231	4,380	5,295
	3	1	8,921	,147	8,630	9,211
		2	7,333	,218	6,902	7,764
		3	6,762	,266	6,235	7,289
2	1	1	8,774	,125	8,527	9,021
		2	6,877	,214	6,453	7,301
		3	4,579	,257	4,070	5,089
	2	1	8,635	,142	8,353	8,917
		2	6,774	,225	6,328	7,220
		3	4,246	,256	3,739	4,753
	3	1	8,429	,171	8,090	8,767
		2	6,972	,243	6,492	7,453
		3	6,425	,284	5,863	6,986

15. Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	8,996	,118	8,762	9,230
		2	6,571	,245	6,086	7,057
		3	3,667	,269	3,135	4,198
	2	1	8,889	,128	8,635	9,143
		2	6,492	,244	6,008	6,976
		3	3,548	,268	3,018	4,078
	3	1	8,575	,173	8,232	8,918
		2	6,750	,244	6,266	7,234
		3	6,163	,293	5,582	6,744
2	1	1	9,206	,083	9,042	9,370
		2	7,619	,193	7,237	8,001
		3	5,738	,237	5,268	6,208
	2	1	9,139	,103	8,935	9,343
		2	7,504	,190	7,127	7,881
		3	5,536	,238	5,065	6,006
	3	1	8,774	,133	8,510	9,038
		2	7,556	,218	7,125	7,986
		3	7,024	,267	6,495	7,553

16. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% ...
						Lower Bound
1	1	1	1	9,278	,149	8,983
			2	6,714	,266	6,188
			3	3,698	,265	3,173
		2	1	9,302	,133	9,037
			2	6,468	,265	5,943
			3	3,786	,276	3,240
		3	1	8,825	,189	8,452
			2	6,952	,256	6,445
			3	6,214	,299	5,622
	2	1	1	9,579	,069	9,443
			2	7,913	,204	7,508
			3	5,952	,250	5,458
		2	1	9,484	,100	9,286
			2	7,976	,190	7,601
			3	5,889	,244	5,406
3		1	9,016	,154	8,712	
		2	7,714	,223	7,272	
		3	7,310	,273	6,769	
2	1	1	1	8,714	,146	8,425
			2	6,429	,253	5,927
			3	3,635	,294	3,053
		2	1	8,476	,173	8,133
			2	6,516	,263	5,996
			3	3,310	,278	2,759
		3	1	8,325	,204	7,922
			2	6,548	,276	6,002
			3	6,111	,319	5,479
	2	1	1	8,833	,130	8,576
			2	7,325	,216	6,897
			3	5,524	,267	4,996
		2	1	8,794	,148	8,500
			2	7,032	,235	6,567
			3	5,183	,275	4,638
3	1	8,532	,170	8,195		
	2	7,397	,245	6,913		
	3	6,738	,290	6,164		

16. Physical.activity * Drinking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

				95% Confidence .	
Physical.activity	Drinking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Upper Bound	
1	1	1	1	9,573	
			2	7,241	
			3	4,223	
		2	1	9,566	
			2	6,994	
			3	4,332	
		3	1	9,199	
			2	7,460	
			3	6,806	
	2	1	1	1	9,716
				2	8,317
				3	6,447
		2	1	1	9,682
				2	8,352
				3	6,371
		3	1	1	9,320
				2	8,156
				3	7,851
2	1	1	1	9,003	
			2	6,930	
			3	4,217	
		2	1	1	8,819
				2	7,036
				3	3,860
		3	1	1	8,729
				2	7,093
				3	6,743
	2	1	1	1	9,090
				2	7,754
				3	6,052
		2	1	1	9,087
				2	7,496
				3	5,727
		3	1	1	8,868
				2	7,881
				3	7,312